

УДК: 17.023.3:37–053.81«20»

orcid.org/0000-0002-7093-5675

orcid.org/0000-0002-4783-7938

orcid.org/0000-0002-5580-7106

D.V. Polezhaev, Y.A. Klimenko, M.Y. Tikhomirov
Volgograd National Academy of Teacher
Professional Development and Retraining;
Poltava V.G.Korolenko National Pedagogical University;
Volgograd State Social and Pedagogical University

PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE INTERGRATED APPROACH TO THE GOAL FORMATION OF THE 21ST CENTURY YOUTH: FOUNDATIONS OF THE CONCEPTUAL DETERMINATION

This paper provides the author's concept connected with the realization of the integrated psychological approach to the goal formation of the youth. The youth context of the establishment of the goal formation in the modern times stresses the topicality of the issue under consideration for the science, education, and culture. Different approaches to the professional self-determination of the 21st century youth are examined as the substantial foundations: directive and motivational; differential and distributional; co-participant, etc.

Key words: personal professional self-determination, integrated psychological approach, motivation, directionality.

Д.В.Полєжаєв, Ю.О.Клименко, М.Ю.Тихомиров ПСИХОЛОГІЧНІ ОСНОВИ ІНТЕГРОВАНОГО ПІДХОДУ ДО ЦІЛЕТВО- РЕННЯ МОЛОДІ ХХІ СТОЛІТТЯ: ОСНОВИ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОЇ ДЕТЕ- РМІНАЦІЇ

У статті представлено авторську концепцію, що пов'язана з реалізацією інтегрованого психологічного підходу до цілетворення молоді. Молодіжний контекст становлення цілетворення на сучасному етапі підкреслює актуальність цієї проблеми для науки, освіти й культури. В якості змістового підґрунтя розглядаються різні підходи професійного самовизначення молоді ХХІ століття: директивно-мотивуючий, диференційно-розподільний, співпричетний та інші.

Ключові слова: професійне самовизначення особистості, інтегрований психологічний підхід, мотивація, спрямованість.

Д.В. Полежаев, Ю.А. Клименко, М.Ю. Тихомиров
**ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО ПОДХОДА К
ЦЕЛЕОБРАЗОВАНИЮ МОЛОДЁЖИ XXI ВЕКА: ОСНОВЫ КОН-
ЦЕПТУАЛЬНОЙ ДЕТЕРМИНАЦИИ**

В работе представлена авторская концепция, связанная с реализацией интегрированного психологического подхода к целеобразованию молодёжи. Молодёжный контекст становления целеобразования в современности подчёркивает актуальность рассматриваемой проблемы для науки, образования и культуры. В качестве содержательных основ рассматриваются различные подходы профессионального самоопределения молодежи XX века: директивно-мотивирующий, дифференциально-распределительный, сопричастный и другие.

Ключевые слова: профессиональное самоопределение личности, интегрированный психологический подход, мотивация, направленность.

Formulation of the problem. The complex study of the goal orientation of the personal professional self-determination as the leading problem of the social and humanitarian sciences is going to involve highlighting a number of structural elements requiring special attention. These are: 1) the focus of the problem and the key part of its solution; 2) the content of the activities of the educator / teacher / tutor as the translator of goal orientations; 3) the key mechanism of the goal orientation. The examination of the stated and some other aspects is tightly connected with the key ideas of several authors concerning the orientation of the activities of the educator / teacher / moderator towards personal influence through motivating, evaluations, and its orientation towards co-operation (support, event-driven interaction).

This criterion presents the substantial foundation of our proposed scientific classification. The name of the psychological approach we are developing considerably reflects the pedagogical solution of the professional self-determination goal orientation problem provided by the authors.

Analysis of recent researches and publications. The author's basis of the concept foundations of the integrative approach requires approaching the most general foundations of the psychological approaches, developed by our forerunners – for marking the common, the specific, and the singular of the concepts in the comparative aspect.

Directive and motivational approach (persuasion, agitation, propaganda of a certain vocational choice). This approach is based on the effectiveness of the educator's / teacher's / tutor's activities of persuasion, ordering, exhortation. The basis of this approach consists of A.S.Makarenko's works on the vocational choice issue [7]. The central discussion regards the problem of the teenager's orientation towards a certain profession needed in the context of the Soviet developing economy of the early 20th century: accelerated industrialization, preparation for military actions, etc. Restoration of the social professional structure

destroyed by the Russian events of the first half of the 20th century required active involvement of the youth in mastering certain professions. In the second half of the 20th century due to the necessity of restoration and development of the economy this approach is still topical and concretized in both purely pedagogical and psychological studies.

The essence of the directive approach is creating the youth's pro-social targets by immersion of the youth in the socially meaningful activities, during which important personal and professional qualities are formed. The meaning of the educative orientation lies in providing the youth with adequate socially oriented alternatives to antisocial lifestyles. Worth highlighting is the fact that A.S.Makarenko managed to offer his delinquent students the targets which allowed the young people to adapt successfully to complex living conditions of the middle 20th century. While, strictly speaking, the domestic pedagogy classic raises and solves the professional orientation problem as the «anti-personality» «re-orientation» problem, till the 1980s the «vocational orientation» practice in the USSR was limited to agitation of school-leavers for choosing certain professions or places of employment [16, 9].

In this case the optant has to interpret the transmitted targets correctly, which inevitably causes resistance. The author remarks: «... my unmasked consultation was met even with some resistance. But I patiently trained them to work and schooling, around themselves they saw new Soviet society, new freedom, new ways for a human. Wide roads opened for them and for all the Soviet youth. First cautiously and then more and more bravely my pupils stepped at them, conquered new spheres, discovered new prospects» [7]. Generally in Makarenko's works we find the understanding of vocational and personal self-determination as the «acculturation» of a certain youth sub-culture to the «adult world».

The problem the educator / teacher / tutor faces is the resistance or even opposition of «the orientated» to the external influence. In line with this approach there has been done a whole range of works of the Soviet period of domestic studies of the vocational self-determination issue of the second half of the 20th century. There is one particularly noteworthy work in this range. This is E.M.Pavlyutenkov's work on the formation of the labor directedness of the choice of profession. The author presents aims and tasks of the pedagogical faculty of «equipping» parents, in particular, with «the system of necessary knowledge and skills». The author also stresses the role of parents, social organizations that play a significant role in the «adequate motivational sphere» formation. The author provides an interesting link to the fact that «lack of adequate motivational sphere» leads to such undesirable outcomes: approximately one fifth of pedagogical university alumni try to avoid school jobs; 20-25 percent express indifference about their future work; there is a constant outflow of

professionals from the teaching work field to other fields of the economy; up to 20 percent of teachers are dissatisfied with their work [11, 107]. In the context of our study this work deals with «targets», not the motives. The young person is oriented towards the future professional activities, a certain professional status and life achievements that receive positive attitude. The arrangement of one's own professional life according to the set targets is considered to be a sign of maturity for people who «... still had real aspirations in their life, still enjoyed free choice of their path» [7].

Differential and distributional approach (evaluation of the optant's suitability for a certain professional field). This approach originates from the general educational concept of locating the student's inclination towards a certain subject field and creating a specific professionally-oriented «educational trajectory». During the initial period of the establishment of the foreign professional orientation the focus was given to distribution and selection of people from the point of view of compliance with a specific position on the basis of complex principles.

The basis of this approach consists of works of J.Holland and D.Super [26], who studies the personality through individual interests, abilities and other qualities appropriate to a range of jobs. He assumes that the structure of individual interests, abilities and other personal qualities creating «Self-Concept» can correspond to the structure of professional tasks and requirements. J.Holland defines 6 personality types – Realistic, Investigative, Social, Conventional, Enterprising, and Artistic, and the environment of the same name. He suggests that every person strives for knowledge in the environment of the corresponding type. [23, 87-102; 24, 1-12]. The typology constructed by Holland is proved by empiric data and shows exceptional validity in the education and profession choice prognosis. Still, both scientists ignore the economic and social influences on the professional self-determination.

The essence of this approach is shown in the original statement of F.Parsons (1909) saying that every person fits a certain professional field, where he can display his abilities to a maximum effect. The optant's personality is assigned a role of an honest testee, who should deal with the personal ability evaluation procedure and the idea of their development through implementing in a specific job with a maximum level of openness and interest. The main problem the representatives of this approach face is the low labor motivation of the subjects, lack of interests or abilities.

This approach has its advantages in working with specific categories of people, for instance, people with special needs, or narrow professional groups. In other words, in the situation of the limited number of professional development options the professional selection criteria become also the specific target selection criteria.

Co-participant approach (the professional formation assistance). At the core of this approach there lie studies of personal development peculiarities, adolescent motivation studies. This approach can embrace works by A.G. Asmolov [2], V.A. Petrovsky [12], E. Erikson [21], L.M. Mitina [8] and others. The approach name stresses the main idea of target orientation mediated by the ideal representation of one person in another. For instance, identity can be regarded as a form of involvement with a group or a social community.

The essence of the approach lies in the postulation of the development (self-development) laws as the primary cause of the human being's mental life, his worldview [12]. The target orientation is not singled out due to sufficiently pronounced centering on personality, development and self-development determining processes. On the contrary, the authors stress undesirability of direct «intervention» or control of self-determination, or directive offer of certain development options. «... the paramount importance is assigned to the activity program (not «work therapy»)» allowing each patient to develop his talents under the guidance of professional teachers, who practice their art with the full responsibility, but do not force the patient to make any hasty vocational choices. It is extremely important that the patient knows his rights and responsibilities, and also the staff's rights and responsibilities [21, 225].

Moreover, the category of teleology (target orientation) is questioned and considered restrictive and limiting the expanse of scientific thought. There have been offers to replace the term «goal-setting» with «self-setting» [12, 280]. The authors [3; 12; 21] highlight key terms («subjectivity», «identity», «social situation of development») as essence of a sort, formation of which create the grounds for real self-determination.

The optant's personality is assigned the role of the active creator of personal inner world, personal Ego-concept (D. Super). It is the young person who is given the responsibility for his choice, successful identity, moratorium choice, whether this choice reflects «non-adaptive activity» (V.A. Petrovsky) or is largely determined by unconscious factors (E. Erikson). The educator / teacher / tutor figure appears as largely a therapist or a researcher figure solving development condition creating tasks. For instance, the educator, according to V.A. Petrovsky's comments, needs to be «a vivid person» or, for example, «a responsible teacher» (E. Erikson), that can cause positive shifts by itself. In other words, the educator / teacher / tutor «creates» the situation and is invisibly present in it as a mediator [12, 340-341].

The problem the representatives of this approach face is the presence of maladjustment tendencies caused, on the one hand, by conditions the subject resides in, and, on the other hand, by his potential abilities. The accent on deep psychological development regularities of this approach makes it unattractive as the basis for psychological and pedagogical practice in the field of profes-

sional self-determination. Indeed, personality comprehension outside the role of «simple agent (social functionary) in the processes of social reproduction» [12, 340] questions the target orientation as a psychological problem proper and puts professional self-determination outside the personal development. The educator is positively moved to the self-development «background», and the personal activity is compared to the influence of «magic universal solvent» (V.A. Petrovsky). Whether this activity acquires socially meaningful orientation in the self-determination aspect (personal or professional) without the educator's active position stays off-screen.

The importance of this approach is, in our view, in the analysis of internal conditions hampering the external goal orientation and highlighting «internal necessities» [4] that realize their own internal development logic without coinciding with the socially dictated logic. Considering the goal orientation problem from the point of view of this approach is fully acceptable for the analysis of breaking, «revolutionary» development points, when the personality is obsessed with crisis – non-adaptive – experiences; to deal with them the personality needs to find its own internal support, for instance, in the form of «reflected subjectivity» or «identity» as experience of co-participation with other people.

Event-driven and co-operational approach (assisting professional self-determination through creating conditions for event-driven co-operation). The basis of this approach consists of theoretical ideas of D.A. Leontiev, S.L. Rubinstein, V.A. Slobodchikov.

The essence of this approach is recognition of the existence of collective principle in a person, the importance of commonality between people not in the way of «reflected subjectivity», but in the way of living, immediate co-existence with others. S.L. Rubinstein stresses that «the real source and driving force of self-consciousness development should be searched in the growing real independence of the individual, which manifests in the change of his relations with people around him» [17, 740-741]. The interesting fact that V.I. Slobodchikov, while describing such communities, uses the term «targets» in the meaning of «everything the activity is oriented at». He remarks, for instance, that «all the types of human social organization are determined by targets. Organization is always oriented at the business: the business is the aim of consolidation» [18]. The personality cannot be imagined without the main three categories – community, consciousness, and activity, which are the universal ways of human existence, the human life [19, 161]. In doing so, the special role is assigned to «co-existence communities»: «... co-existence communities should be perceived as «living organs» of mental capacity, as special channels, through which this capacity is externalized. And if a person does not get into a certain community, or falls out of it, then one of his organs is not formed, or gets damaged; this organ connects the person to the human world, to culture;

thus certain abilities fail to form, and the development of these abilities is made possible through this very channel» [19, 169].

The optant's personality is assigned the following role: «*During the meeting, the occurrence of the child's plastic organicity and the adult's action program the formation of individual abilities starts* (and so does the content of the individual psyche), more and more freedom from its *indeterminacy* and more and more freedom for proper definiteness and belonging to the human society is got» [19, 180]. In this extract italic type is used for the important interpretation of target orientation problem as the original *indeterminacy* of development, overcome by the personality with the help of the human society.

As the problem of target orientation from the point of view of this approach we can consider the problem of individualization, individual activity style organization, creating a stand-alone individualized development space, i.e. self-formation in the role of the participant of event-driven community as opposed to symbiotic merging.

This approach allows ascertaining structural peculiarities of socially meaningful supportive relations, connections. We can come across a similar idea in J.Nuttin, who proposes a «relation» motivation model, stressing that «the focus of its attention should be behavioral relations connecting the individual with his physical and social environment» [10, 98]. Besides, K. Levin remarks on the importance of social interaction.

Still, no approach provides the whole view of the professional self-determination target orientation problem due to the scientists placing their accents on other content aspects. For instance, the directive approach places the biggest accent on the topical social and economic situation and each society member's contribution to the solution of social and economic problems, reaching socially meaningful aims. Differential and distributive approach helps to comprehend objective limitations connected with human abilities to perform his professional duties properly. Co-participant approach allows regarding crucial, crisis points of the personal development as important conditions determining the professional self-determination dynamics. Finally, event-driven and co-operational approach determines inviolability of the principle of regarding professional activity as creative and socially important, as opposed to the principle of individualistic «self-realization» and competitiveness as the fundamental foundation of development.

The main material research. The approach we offer tries to fully analyze the target orientation problem through synthesis of the most important and significant ideas of the professional self-determination target orientation. Firstly, we select the idea of correspondence between a specific pedagogical strategy from each of the approaches and the orientation situation. Thus, directive approach is more appropriate for the candidates non-motivated (non-oriented) to

their profession and job in general; differential and distributional approach is for candidates oriented for their profession and for job in general, who still unrealistically imagine their own abilities, resources, and the chosen job content in general; co-participant approach is most effective in the crisis self-determination situation; event-driven and co-operational approach is for the person getting his own individuality through socially meaningful activity in the social community, having already started his career and experiencing the professional adaptation stage [6].

Still, none of the above-mentioned approaches stresses the necessity for complex study of the target orientation problem. Then, the professional self-determination studies are oriented at specific professional communities and do not stress the problems of personality development proper, and personal development studies are, in turn, oriented at identification of, first of all, general psychological patterns typical for different professional groups. It complicates the search for means and methods of forming, developmental work, the general character of which is limited by specific features of the job content.

Thus, there appears the necessity of addressing the professional self-determination target orientation problem from other points of view. From one hand, professional self-determination is conditioned by moments of mutual transition of internal and external determination. From the other hand, the personal activity involves omnidirectional character of activity, which creates the internal contradiction potential forcing the personality to create its own, first and foremost, cognitive strategy of its overcoming [1]. Dealing with the target orientation problem should be based on ascertaining the definite space, where the personality creates specific «target orientations» as marks for specific ways of professional and personal development. As one cannot violate the ban one is unaware about, one cannot consciously choose a specific option of professional future, if one does not have an idea about this option. The pedagogical strategy allowing flexible «inclusion» of certain «targets» by provoking their discussion and studies during different kinds of psychological and pedagogical assistance, psychological support is the most productive in the social and economic conditions of modern Russia.

Integrated (author's) approach. The basis of our approach consists of works by D.V. Polezhaiev [13], M.Y. Tikhomirov [20], N.S. Priazhnikov and E.Y. Priazhnikova [16], N.I. Nepomniashchaia [9] and other authors, the important content of their studies being the attempt to fully interpret the personal professional self-determination on the basis of synthesis of main ideas of different approaches.

The principle foundations of our approach towards the solution of the professional self-determination target orientation problem of the 21st century youth are described by the following research position. Professional self-

determination viewed as «one's own identification in the profession» cannot be fully determined by internal «self-development» processes or the necessity of subordinating it to social and economic development tasks. Professional self-determination should be perceived as personal movement «in the space of target» set, on the one hand, by logic of the general mental development and by the social community development, on the other. This movement occurs in turn in the order determined by «orienteeing» logic (the stages of this movement are mentioned earlier).

The condition for successful professional self-determination is concentration, focus of the young person on targets in the context of his current situation (receiving professional education), the remote perspective and their combination with personal aspirations and opportunities. For this purpose, the student is offered different elements for creating various forms of professional and life perspectives.

Our approach regards the personality of the young person in the process of self-determination as the subject, which actively and selectively evaluates and internalizes offered aims, values, motives and transforms them into targets of the personal professional and life development.

The issues that can be identified from the view-point of this approach are linked to: 1) forming targets of the optant belonging to an asocial system and difficulties of the target transformation; 2) target system immaturity connected with the targets' excessive breadth and ambiguity; unrealistic goals, motives, and values; a gap between targets of professional and life development; 3) contradiction between prevailing pro-social target system and existing social and economic realities (lack of demand for the particular profession, disproportionately low remuneration, etc.). In the context of this study we refer mostly to the second and third problem.

The value of our approach lies in development of principles and criteria for creating effective development programs for professional self-determination targets. For instance, the effectiveness of the professional self-determination activation strategy [15] is determined by integration of above-mentioned approaches. The activation methods include motivating as offering more socially advantageous targets, client (optant) resource evaluation, emotional support in decision-making situations, event-driven co-operation during joint future development discussion.

Pre-pilot target study with the help of questionnaire method allows us to confirm the legitimacy of our classification of theoretical approaches to professional self-determination analysis. The respondent's type of professional self-determination targets was determined on the basis of the content of the sentence finished by the respondent: «I am studying at the pedagogical university and getting pedagogical training in order to...». The respondents rated the educa-

tional process quality and their personal activity on a five-point scale. The results of the questionnaire result classification mostly fit into the above-mentioned systematization of the approaches to professional self-determination target orientation. The results of the respondents' answers to additional questions allow us to suggest that the accomplished classification of targets has empirical value in the aspect of the analysis of professional formation of beginning teachers. Meanwhile, the trend of the surveyed indicators is of non-linear nature. Still, as the target system develops, the level of material demands of intending teachers moves increasingly closer to the economic realities. The attitude to the university educational process organization further improves; accordingly, personal learning and professional activities intensify. Finally, at the higher target development level the attitude to the university and personal learning efforts becomes more critical. One can say that during the last years of university studies there happens the first collision of previously created targets with life realities.

We can see that the majority (55%) includes students with «ambiguous» and «crisis» targets. It means the necessity of flexible approach to the target orientation, which allows the young people to set their own priorities.

Conclusions and recommendations for further research. The preliminary findings of our conceptual study. Professional self-determination targets are specific results of the personal professional career, which serve as meaningful criteria of professional life planning, on the one hand, and professional and personal development options, on the other hand. The introduction of this notion allows ascertaining the content of terms used to describe professional self-determination: motives, aims, orientation, value orientations.

The main role of targets is structuring the entire picture of professional career, reflecting future development options. The main approaches, in the framework of which we study the problem of professional self-determination target orientation, are based on the corresponding pedagogical strategy of psychological and pedagogical assistance, guidance, support for the young people. The initial study shows the necessity of using flexible work strategy, which allows working with the heterogeneous public and dealing with different target types. It is the spontaneous work with the audience that allows us to create conditions for target orientation of the young people.

References

1. Анцыферова Л.И. Личность в тяжёлых жизненных условиях: переосмысление, преобразование ситуаций и психологическая защита / Л.И. Анцыферова // Психологический журнал. — 1994. — № 1. — С. 3-19.

2. Асмолов А.Г. Психология личности: принципы общепсихологического анализа / А.Г. Асмолов. — М.: Смысл, 2001. — 416 с.
3. Божович Л.И. Психологические закономерности формирования личности в онтогенезе / Л.И. Божович // Вопросы философии. — 1976. — № 6. — С. 45-53.
4. Василюк Ф.Е. Психология переживания (анализ преодоления критических ситуаций) / Ф.Е. Василюк. — М.: Изд-во Моск. ун-та, 1984. — 200 с.
5. Климов Е.А. О феномене профессиональной относительности образа мира / Е.А. Климов // Вестник Московского университета. Серия 14. Психология. — 1995. — № 1. — С. 8-18.
6. Макаренко А.С. Трудовое воспитание / А.С. Макаренко. — М.: Просвещение, 1964. — 246 с.
7. Митина Л.М. Личностное и профессиональное развитие человека в новых социально-экономических условиях / Л.М. Митина // Вопросы психологии. — 1997. — № 4. — С. 28-38.
8. Непомнящая Н.И. Целостно-личностный подход к изучению человека / Н.И. Непомнящая // Вопросы психологии. — 2005. — № 1. — С. 116-126.
9. Нюттен Ж. Мотивация, действие и перспектива будущего / Ж. Нюттен [под ред. Д.А. Леонтьева]. — М.: Смысл, 2004. — 608 с.
10. Павлютенков Е.М. Формирование мотивов выбора профессии / Е.М. Павлютенков. — К.: Рад. шк., 1980. — 144 с.
11. Петровский В.А. Введение в психологию / В.А. Петровский. — М.: Изд. центр «Академия», 1996. — 270 с.
12. Полежаев Д.В. Личность в этнокультурном пространстве: ментальный аспект социальной теории / Д.В. Полежаев // Культура. Образование. Наука. Сборник научных трудов [под ред. проф. Д.В. Полежаева]. — М.: Планета, 2014. — Вып. IX. — С. 9-20.
13. Полежаев Д.В. Русский менталитет: социально-философское осмысление: монография / Д.В. Полежаев. — Волгоград: Изд-во ВолГУ, 2007. — 370 с.
14. Пряжников Н.С. Профессиональное и личностное самоопределение / Н.С. Пряжников. — М.: Институт практической психологии; Воронеж: НПО «МОДЭК», 1996. — 256 с.
15. Пряжникова Е.Ю. Профорентация / Е.Ю. Пряжникова, Н.С. Пряжников. — М.: Академия, 2007. — 496 с.
16. Рубинштейн С.Л. Основы общей психологии / С.Л. Рубинштейн. — СПб.: Питер, 2002. — 720 с. — (Серия «Мастера психологии»).
17. Слободчиков В.И. Проблема научного обеспечения инновационной деятельности в образовании. Концептуальные основания / В.И. Слободчиков. — Киров, 2003. — 32 с.
18. Слободчиков В.И. Психология развития человека / В.И. Слободчиков. — М.: Школьная пресса, 2000. — 416 с.
19. Тихомиров М.Ю. Целевые ориентиры профессионального самоопределения личности: методологические основания / М.Ю. Тихомиров, Д.В. Полежаев // Историко-педагогічні студії: науковий часопис. — К.: Вид-во НПУ імені М.П. Драгоманова, 2014. — Вип. 8. — С. 270-274.

20. Эриксон Э. Идентичность: юность и кризис / Э. Эриксон. — М.: Изд. группа «Прогресс», 1996. — 344 с.
21. Holland L. Award for Distinguished Scientific Application of Psychology / L. Holland. — American Psychologist. — 2008. — № 63. — p. 672-674.
22. Holland J.L. Why interest inventories are also personality inventories / Holland J.L. — Palo Alto, CA: Davies-Black, 1999. — P. 87-102.
23. Holland J. The Vocational Identity Scale: A diagnostic and treatment tool / J.Holland, J.Johnston, N.Asama // Journal of Career Assessment. — 1993. — № 1. — P. 1-12.
24. Moser U. Zur psychoanalytischen Theorie der Berufswahl: Sublimierung, Identifizierung und berufliche Identität / U. Moser // Psychologie. Schweizerisch Zeitschrift für Psychologie. — 1963. — № 1. — S. 1-18.
25. Super D.E. Vocational Development: A Framework of Research / D.E. Super — N. Y., 1957 — 245 p.

Надійшла до редколегії 25.02.2016